

ISic0823

Statue base for Hieron II of Syracuse

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone (area of Taormina?)

Object

statue base

Editor

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Autopsy

2006.04; 2013.10.02

Last Change

2018-02-23 - Jonathan Prag checked EpiDoc, edited text, app and trans div, added bibl

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6489

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Βασιλέος ἀγε[μόνος]
2. Ἱέρωνος Ἱεροκλέος
3. Συρακόσιοι θεοῖς πᾶσι

Apparatus

Text of Kaibel (IG)

ἀγε[ομένου], Dittenberger

Translation (en)

The Syracusans (dedicate this statue) of the king and hegemon Hieron, son of Hierokles, to all the gods

Commentary

As John Ma, *Statues and Cities* (Oxford 2013) 20 n.27 notes, this is an anomalous instance of an honorific dedication where the honorand is in the genitive

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0002 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 56.1103.1.1

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5368

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezzenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 3231

Dittenberger, W. 1915-1924. Sylloge inscriptionum graecarum. Leipzig. At no.427

De Sensi Sestito, G. 1977. Gerone II. Un monarca ellenistico in Sicilia. *Kleio.* Palermo. At 82

Libertini, G 1929. Il regio museo archeologico di Siracusa. *Guide dei musei italiani.* Roma. At 123

Dimartino, A. 2006. Per una revisione dei documenti epigrafici siracusani pertinenti al regno di Ierone II. In Michelini, C.(eds.), *Guerra e pace in Sicilia e nel Mediterraneo antico (VIII-III sec. a.C.). Arte, prassi e teoria della pace e della guerra.* Pisa. pp. 703-717. At no.1.1

Prag, J.R.W. 2017. Un unpublished funerary inscription with bichrome painted relief lettering from Hellenistic Syracuse (I.Sicily 3387). *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik.* 203: 119-130. At 122 fig.5

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